

Post-publication review of 'Ballistic Majorana Superconductivity', Zhang et al. Nature communications 2017

Sergey Frolov, Vincent Mourik & Kun Zuo

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What this Analysis is Based On

These slides critique the published claims of Zhang et al, Nature Communications 2017, based on published data and additional data shared with us by corresponding authors of the paper. The additional data were provided to us in a mixture of numerical format (permitting independent replotting) and laboratory-notebook-style powerpoints containing data as images. Full data have not been shared.

What are the main claims and statements of the article?

ARTICLE

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OPEN

Ballistic superconductivity in semiconductor nanowires

Hao Zhang^{1,2,*}, Önder Gül^{1,2,*}, Sonia Conesa-Boj^{1,2,3}, Michał P. Nowak^{1,2,4}, Michael Wimmer^{1,2}, Kun Zuo^{1,2}, Vincent Mourik^{1,2}, Folkert K. de Vries^{1,2}, Jasper van Veen^{1,2}, Michiel W.A. de Moor^{1,2}, Jouri D.S. Bommer^{1,2}, David J. van Woerkom^{1,2}, Diana Car³, Sébastien R. Plissard^{2,3}, Erik P.A.M. Bakkers^{1,2,3}, Marina Quintero-Pérez^{1,5}, Maja C. Cassidy^{1,2}, Sebastian Koelling³, Srijit Goswami^{1,2}, Kenji Watanabe⁶, Takashi Taniguchi⁶ & Leo P. Kouwenhoven^{1,2,7}

Semiconductor nanowires have opened new research avenues in quantum transport owing to their confined geometry and electrostatic tunability. They have offered an exceptional testbed for superconductivity, leading to the realization of hybrid systems combining the macroscopic quantum properties of superconductors with the possibility to control charges down to a single electron. These advances brought semiconductor nanowires to the forefront of efforts to realize topological superconductivity and Majorana modes. A prime challenge to benefit from the topological properties of Majoranas is to reduce the disorder in hybrid nanowire devices. Here we show ballistic superconductivity in InSb semiconductor nanowires. Our structural and chemical analyses demonstrate a high-quality interface between the nanowire and a NbTiN superconductor that enables ballistic transport. This is manifested by a quantized conductance for normal carriers, a strongly enhanced conductance for Andreev-reflecting carriers, and an induced hard gap with a significantly reduced density of states. These results pave the way for disorder-free Majorana devices.

Main text, introduction:

Here we show ballistic superconductivity in InSb semiconductor nanowires. Our structural and chemical analyses demonstrate a high-quality interface between the InSb nanowire and a NbTiN superconductor. The high-quality interface enables ballistic transport manifested by a quantized conductance for normal carriers, and a strongly enhanced conductance for Andreev-reflecting carriers at energies below the superconducting gap. Our numerical analysis indicates a mean free path of several micrometres, implying ballistic transport of Andreev pairs in the proximitized nanowire. Finally, tunnelling conductance reveals an induced hard gap with a significantly reduced density of states. These results constitute a substantial improvement

Main claim:

Ballistic superconductivity = proximity induced superconductivity in semiconductor with a long mean free path.

Long mean free path = several micrometers, exact number not specified

Main claim is enabled by three 'sub-claims':

1. QPC observed
2. Hard gap observed
3. Andreev enhancement observed

An equally important 4th claim is present later in the text:

4. Absence of quantum dots and any other localization effects

Statements on ballistic behaviour

From results, ballistic transport section, pg 3:

stepping the gate voltage V_{gate} applied to the global back gate (Fig. 1b). We first of all note that throughout the entire gate voltage range in Fig. 2 we do not observe signs of the formation of unintentional quantum dots or any other localization effects resulting from potential fluctuations. Instead, we observe conductance plateaus at $2e^2/h$ for all devices, typical for ballistic transport and a clear signature of disorder-free devices. For a sufficiently negative gate voltage the non-covered nanowire sec-

From results, theoretical simulation section, pg 3:

device with a particularly flat plateau. Comparing Fig. 3b and Fig. 3c, we find good agreement for a mean free path of several micrometres. This implies ballistic transport of Andreev pairs in the proximitized wire section underneath the superconductor, whose length far exceeds the length of the non-covered wire between the contacts (see also Supplementary Fig. 5). Andreev

From results, theoretical simulation section, pg 4:

In Fig. 3d,e, we compare a conductance measurement similar to the one in Fig. 2a with the simulation of a ballistic device. The overall agreement indicates a very low disorder strength for our devices.

Absence of proof of QPC behaviour

We observe that proof for the claimed observation of a QPC is lacking, and this invalidates the paper in its entirety.

The key problems are twofold:

1) A diagnostic set of measurements required to unambiguously demonstrate a QPC is missing for all 5 devices shown in the main text.

These measurements are:

- a) Bias spectroscopy up to significant voltages of the order of the subband spacing, i.e. in the 10 to 20 mV range – only small bias ranges of $\sim \pm 2$ mV were studied.
- b) Study of multiple QPC plateaus – only a single feature ascribed to be a ‘plateau’ was studied.
- c) Spin splitting of QPC plateaus – the magnet field evolution of the feature ascribed to be a ‘plateau’ was not studied.

1) Observations inconsistent with the QPC interpretation, namely localization effects due to weakly confined quantum dots, have been concealed. This is achieved through:

- a) The selection of certain devices for inclusion in the article
- b) The subsequent selection of specific datasets obtained from these devices
- c) The processing (cropping, smoothing, color scale tweaking, averaging and conductance calibration) of these selected datasets to appear like a QPC.

A message of (near) perfect quantization in all devices is conveyed. In reality, there is clear evidence for contradictory interpretations present.

These various flaws are substantiated in the following slides.

Absence of proof of QPC behavior:

Selection of devices for inclusion in the study

From results, ballistic transport section, pg 3:

stepping the gate voltage V_{gate} applied to the global back gate (Fig. 1b). We first of all note that throughout the entire gate voltage range in Fig. 2 we do not observe signs of the formation of unintentional quantum dots or any other localization effects resulting from potential fluctuations. Instead, we observe conductance plateaus at $2e^2/h$ for all devices, typical for ballistic transport and a clear signature of disorder-free devices. For a sufficiently negative gate voltage the non-covered nanowire sec-

Find the QPC – plots from laboratory notebook powerpoint file shared by corresponding authors; full data not shared

Devices A, B, C and E are part of a larger set of 21 individual NS-junctions from a single fabrication batch. Most of these junctions were studied only briefly with the dataset on this slide being the only dataset of note. These data show a continuum, going from many bright resonances in some junctions to only a few faint ones in others. Any 'QPC'-device should have been scrutinized for the presence of such resonances. The impression that the devices are very clean is misleading – most junctions show unambiguous evidence for localization.

Legend
 Green border: NS-junction selected for inclusion in paper.
 Magenta border: examples of NS-junctions with many clear resonances
 Remaining datasets are 'in between'.

The two plots on the left from the laboratory notebook style powerpoint provided by the corresponding authors are both followed by the comment '*Bad device - quantum dots*'. They show obvious resonances.

The plot on the right, also from this powerpoint, is from the device called B in the paper. There is a broad faint resonance present which we have indicated with a black dotted line.

There is no fundamental difference between these devices.

Device B

Absence of proof of QPC behavior:

Lacking of a diagnostic dataset

A diagnostic set of measurements required to unambiguously demonstrate a QPC is missing for all 5 devices shown in the main text. These measurements are:

- a) Bias spectroscopy up to significant voltages of the order of the subband spacing, i.e. in the 10 to 20 mV range – only small bias ranges of $\sim\pm 2$ mV were studied.
- a) Study of multiple QPC plateaus – only a single feature ascribed to be a ‘plateau’ was studied.
- b) Spin splitting of QPC plateaus – the magnet field evolution of the feature ascribed to be a ‘plateau’ was not studied

Instead, for all devices, only a single, or very few, V_{gate} vs source-drain V_{bias} conductance dataset was generated, in a limited gate voltage range (not allowing assessing higher QPC plateaus), of a limited bias voltage range. Some of these devices were studied in an applied magnetic field, but only for features inside or of the scale of the superconducting gap, i.e. not at all in the gate and source-drain bias voltage regimes relevant to study a QPC.

It should be noted that plateau-like features are common in these type of devices due to unintentional quantum dot states. Furthermore, the value of conductance at such a plateau can be adjusted by an arbitrary offset (a series resistance). This is why a diagnostic dataset is key.

The lack of such a comprehensive dataset for each device in which QPC behavior is claimed is especially troubling given that the devices showed clear localization behavior.

Previous activities of the Kouwenhoven team on establishing QPC

PI and corresponding author Kouwenhoven has a career long experience with experimentally establishing QPC

Earlier work of the Kouwenhoven group includes a 2012 article on a QPC in an InSb nanowire

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PHYSICAL REVIEW LETTERS

29 FEBRUARY 1988

Quantized Conductance of Point Contacts in a Two-Dimensional Electron Gas

B. J. van Wees

Department of Applied Physics, Delft University of Technology, 2628 CJ Delft, The Netherlands

H. van Houten, C. W. J. Beenakker, and J. G. Williamson,
Philips Research Laboratories, 5600 LA Eindhoven, The Netherlands

L. P. Kouwenhoven and D. van der Marel

Department of Applied Physics, Delft University of Technology, 2628 CJ Delft, The Netherlands

and

C. T. Foxon

Philips Research Laboratories, Redhill, Surrey RH1 5HA, United Kingdom

(Received 31 December 1987)

On the right two figures from the 2012 paper, demonstrating three key measurements missing in this current paper: (1) bias spectroscopy to $\sim \pm 15$ mV, across to (2) multiple QPC plateaus, and subsequently, (3) the study of spin splitting of the QPC plateaus as a function of magnetic field.

This methodology was applied and propagated by Kouwenhoven's team, specifically in the context of nanowires, as early as 2012.

NANO LETTERS

Letter

pubs.acs.org/NanoLett

Quantized Conductance in an InSb Nanowire

Ilse van Weperen,[†] Sébastien P. Plissard,[‡] Erik P. A. M. Bakkers,^{†,‡} Sergey M. Frolov,^{†,§} and Leo P. Kouwenhoven^{*,†}

Figure 3. Voltage bias spectroscopy. (a) Conductance as a function of

Figure 4. Development of the conductance plateaus in magnetic field. (a) Conductance g as a function of gate voltage V_g at B between 0 and

Evidence for contemporary activities of corresponding authors Zhang, Gül and Kouwenhoven on thoroughly establishing QPC in nanowires

NANO LETTERS

Letter
pubs.acs.org/NanoLett

Conductance Quantization at Zero Magnetic Field in InSb Nanowires

Jakob Kamhuber,[†] Maja C. Cassidy,[†] Hao Zhang,[†] Önder Gül,[†] Fei Pei,[†] Michiel W. A. de Moor,[†] Bas Nijholt,[†] Kenji Watanabe,[‡] Takashi Taniguchi,[‡] Diana Car,^{||} Sébastien R. Plissard,^{†,§,||} Erik P. A. M. Bakkers,^{†,||} and Leo P. Kouwenhoven,[†]

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The article was submitted early 2016. The first complete draft of the initial paper (prior to splitting in nat com and nat nano) was circulated March 2016. All three corresponding authors had just before collaborated on an experiment thoroughly establishing QPC, demonstrating 3 key measures: quantization in large bias spectroscopy, multiple conductance plateaus, spin splitting of conductance plateaus.

All three corresponding authors were co-author on this Nanoletters article.

From the 2016 nanoletters paper:

(1) Bias spectroscopy to high bias, (2) across multiple conductance plateaus

Figure 2. (a) Color-plot of the differential conductance $G = dI/dV_{\text{bias}}$

(3) Study of spin splitting of multiple conductance plateaus

Figure 3. (a) Differential conductance $G = dI/dV_{\text{bias}}$ and (b) transconductance dG/dV_{gate} as a function of magnetic field along B_z

Why did the 3 corresponding authors deviate from their previously established methodology of proving QPC? Why are all the crucial measurements absent in this study?

The lead authors realized the need for more rigorous experiments to claim QPC at the time of the experiment

Right: Slide 40 from 'Field363324_v2.pptx', a laboratory notebook style powerpoint from the time of the experiment (**October 2015**) shared with us in 2021 by the corresponding authors. Note the encircled statement (red highlighting by us): **the need for high bias data to claim QPC appears to be explicitly acknowledged – yet such data have never been shared with us (if, that is, they have been acquired at all).**

Below: We show part of a slide (slide 22 from 'wire meeting 20151005.pptx') shown at a lab meeting 05-10-2015 (red highlighting by us). **QPC behavior was being claimed and presented in the exact same timeframe as doubts were being expressed in the corresponding log. The fact that most wires were full of quantum dots remained hidden.**

up to $\Delta = 0.9$ meV hard induced gap in N-NW-S devices

zero-bias conductance suppression up to 35
comparable to half-shell InAs/Al epitaxial wires (50)

quantized conductance in many wires
significant conductance increase at zero-bias (up to $1.75 G_0$)

no quantum dots

Absence of proof of QPC behavior:

Evidence for suppression of undesirable observations

In the following slides, we focus on a number of problematic issues.

Figure 2 & device B

Same data, version from lab notebook style powerpoint

- There are important differences between the colorscale plot shown in Fig 2 a and the version present in the laboratory notebook powerpoint shared by the authors (and confirmed in our own plotting). These are (all indicated above with magenta arrows):
- 1) The faint broad resonance is clearer visible.
 - 2) A sharp feature at the 'gap edge' reminiscent of an ABS associated with a quantum dot state is hidden due to saturation of the colorscale in the paper figure.
 - 3) The dataset is smoothed and in combination with colorscale tweaking, as a result the sharp dip in the middle is not well visible.

All three aspects directly contradict the simplistic QPC + Andreev enhancement interpretation.

Data averaged between
 $V_{\text{bias}} = -1.85$ and -2.15 mV

Data averaged between
 $V_{\text{bias}} = +1.85$ and $+2.15$ mV

Average of positive and
negative V_{bias} data

Figure 2d contains a fabricated plateau

G_N is averaged over a voltage bias window. This is in itself already a non-standard procedure.

However, if one averages around $+2$ mV or -2 mV bias, there is no plateau. The conductance either monotonously increase (-2 mV, top left), or shows a small broad peak ($+2$ mV, top right) due to the passing resonance.

To generate the impression of a quantized plateau, the two curves had to be averaged together (bottom left). There is no unambiguous evidence for a plateau in device B.

('Wed Oct 07 22:13:29 2015', 'W01SN2_W10_plateau_B=0mT_Vg-Scan_1.dat')

('Thu Oct 08 10:55:10 2015', 'W01SN2_W10_plateau_B=200mT_Vg-Scan_1.dat')

Device B – subgap states at finite magnetic field

('Thu Oct 08 23:38:05 2015', 'W01SN2_W10_plateau_B=400mT_Vg-Scan_1.dat')

Note how the faintly visible subgap states in the tunneling regime below $1 \cdot G_0$ conductance become pronounced upon applying a small magnetic field of a few hundred mT due to their dispersal to lower energy.

Presence of such subgap states directly contradicts the simple ideal superconducting QPC picture claimed throughout the main text. Instead, it suggests the presence of weakly confined quantum dots somewhere between the tunnel barrier and the superconductor semiconductor interface. This is in direct contradiction to the earlier claim 'We first of all note that throughout the entire gate voltage range in Fig. 2 we do not observe signs of the formation of unintentional quantum dots or any other localization effects resulting from potential fluctuations.'

Yet, their presence was not discussed in the main text nor supplementary figure caption despite clear evidence being present in this and all other devices.

Figure 2e & Device C

Figure panel is a retake of a larger dataset. The gate voltage range is now restricted compared to the large dataset taken just before. The smaller range creates a better impression compared to theory curves in Figure 3b.

This section, not present in the paper, compares less favorably with numerics in figure 3b because G_S dips below G_N . In figure 3, instead a linecut from device D is shown.

More on Figure 3 and Device C

The colorplot in panel d originates from Device C, and is utilised in a side-by-side comparison with theory result. This particular device is preferred over Device D, presumably because it creates a visually more favourable comparison.

However, in panel c, a linecut from device D is preferred, because of a more favourable comparison to theory curves (see also the previous page demonstrating why linecuts from panel d/device C compare less favourable).

No justification is given anywhere why data from various devices is mixed together to create the most visually appealing comparisons in figures. A single coherent story is presented, which is not well-supported by data from individual devices.

Here we compare the various panels from various devices. The visually most appealing comparison was made to theory, to suggest a good fit. In reality, when looking at linecuts (device C) or full dataset (device D) of the individual devices, the comparison is much less favourable.

For **device D**, there are significant subgap states in the tunneling regime that are only visible in the colorplots. These contradict the simple QPC model and are consequently absent in the numerics. Furthermore, the charge jump visible was cut by removing 10 traces from the data, and the conductance correction through series resistances was partially incorrect and deviated from what was stated in the methods section, resulting in the plateau (black line in panel 3C) favourably aligning exactly with $1 \cdot G_0$, the quantized value.

Device C does not compare well with theory and no QPC is demonstrated.

Below the dataset from the supplementary information is shown. The angle of the 3D plot does not reveal an important features of this dataset. The central 'Andreev enhancement' **does not cover the whole width** of the presumed 'induced gap', instead, it is a broad peak in the center of the gap. The waterfall plot on the left demonstrates this. Furthermore, it shows 'shoulders' inside the gap – discrete subgap states. See also next slide for our own colorplots of these data. These aspects contradict the numerical results.

Figure S1

ct 07 22:13:29 2015', 'W01SN2_W10_plateau_B=0mT_Vg-Scan_1.dat') : 08 17:16:39 2015', 'W01SN2_W10_plateau_B=300mT_Vg-Scan_1.dat')

Left: same plot as Fig 3b, with a zoom in on the ‘enhancement’, no smoothing. Note the faintly visible subgap states whenever the conductance is $\sim 1 \cdot G_0$ or smaller.

Right: $B=300$ mT, same settings as Fig3b, clear subgap states crossing at the position of the ‘enhancement’ – what is visible already within the gap at 0 mT has now evolved into clear low energy states crisscrossing around the initial ‘enhancement’ location.

These data suggest that weakly localized states (presumably due to weakly localized quantum dots between barrier and interface) are present causing temporary enhancements when they are near zero bias. No clear evidence for a QPC is present, there is no high bias data, no data revealing multiple plateaus, and no data revealing spin splitting of the plateaus.

The full data on device C do not provide evidence for the presence of a QPC.

Device D: Figure 3c and S1d,i,n

Overview of issues with Device D:

1. In the main text, subgap states are not mentioned and not shown. They are, however, quite significant as can be seen in the supplementary figures. This in itself contradicts the simple QPC + Andreev enhancement narrative conveyed in the text. Also, some tens of datasets exist at finite B, focusing on subgap features. They all come across as rather messy, with many subgaps states crisscrossing the gap. This is not compatible with the 'pristine QPC' narrative of the text.
1. A charge jump was removed by cutting out a section of 10 IV curves and pasting the dataset together, without disclosure, affecting Fig 3c and S1d,i,n.
1. The bias axis is erroneously corrected for a different value of set-up related series resistance than the conductance value itself.
1. Contrarily to the statement in the methods section, this dataset is not corrected for a series resistance of 0.5 kOhm. Although this specific value is of course arbitrary, a value of 0 kOhm is unphysical. Typical estimates originating from fitting multiple quantized plateaus to the quantized values (something impossible here, because there are no plateaus measured) range in the hundred of Ohms to few kOhms regime. Implementing the same 0.5 kOhm value as for the other devices and correcting for 3. above we arrive at a normal state conductance exceeding $1 \cdot G_0$ by $\sim 5\%$. **The corresponding authors have since argued in a draft Readme intended for public release that $1 \cdot G_0$ is exceeded because the bias value (0.8-1.0 mV) used to determine G_N is not sufficiently large to determine G_N accurately. This is an ad-hoc post-publication suggestion that cannot be verified due to the lack of data. Simply put the absence of high bias data completely undermines this paper's claims in several respects, unreliable extraction of G_N being one of these.**

Figure 4: Device A and E

Figure 4 conveys a message of the data fitting perfectly to a well-known, simple theory first put forward by Beenakker. This theory describes Andreev enhancement in a perfect QPC in the single subband regime. See some exact quotes from the main text on the left.

The Figure has one panel originating from device E, the rest come from device A.

From results, hard superconducting gap, pg 4:

$G_n = 2e^2/h \times T$. Figure 4a shows excellent agreement between the calculated and measured subgap conductance up to the point where the measured Andreev enhancement is reduced due to subband mixing. The highest transmission probability obtained from Andreev enhancement sets a lower bound on the interface transparency. Our typical enhancement factor of 1.5 (Figs 2d and 3c) implies an interface transparency ~ 0.93 and our record value of 1.9 (Fig. 2e) gives a transparency larger than 0.98 (see Measurement setup and data analysis in Methods).

of dI/dV for successively lower conductances. The subgap conductance suppression reaches $G_s/G_n \sim 1/50$, a value comparable to the results obtained with epitaxial Al²³. A comparison between the measured subgap conductance and Beenakker's theory (without any fit parameters) is shown in Fig. 4d. The excellent agreement over three orders of magnitude in conductance implies that the subgap conductance is very well described by Andreev processes and no other transport mechanisms are involved^{23,24}. The lowest conductance

Device E (Fig 4a and S1e,j,o)

('Mon Sep 28 03:44:05 2015', 'W02NS2_W15NS2_2Dgate_1.dat')

Left: same data as shown in S1. Right: zoom in scan on tunneling regime.

Both datasets convey a simple picture: a subgap riddled with discrete subgap states. Likely the so-called Andreev enhancement is simply a broadening and clustering of these subgaps states upon the passing of broad, faint transient resonance and no efforts have been undertaken to resolve or discuss this.

These data invalidate the usage of the simple Beenakker formalism, it does not apply to this system where some form of localization is evident. Any quantitative claims based on this approach are invalid, and the 'hard gap' claim is not reliable, there are many discrete subgap states in the tunneling regime.

Device A (Fig 4b,c,d and S1a,f,k)

The same arguments of subgap states invalidating the Beenakker formalism apply to device A. In fact, a rather dramatically dispersing subgap resonance is visible on top of many resonances more stable in energy. Applying a modest magnetic field moves all these subgap resonances to lower energy, as was the case for all other devices studied at finite magnetic field. The 3D waterfall plot does not reveal this very well due to angle.

These data cannot be used for fitting to such a simple theory as the Beenakker formula and directly contradict the hard gap claim.

Device A - Fig 4d

Panel 4d underwent highly non-trivial manipulations that were not disclosed.

Note that the whole approach is not sensible anyway because of the myriad of subgap states present.

The curves at finite magnetic field (green, blue, purple) were taken from a dataset that did not extend beyond the superconducting gap edge. Therefore, G_N could not be determined from that data.

Instead, G_N from the black curve at $B = 0$ T was taken, and used for the other 3 curves as well.

Besides this, all finite magnetic field curves were shifted along the gate axis to overlap with the $B = 0$ T data, presumably to correct for a charge jump.

Both procedures are highly non-trivial. If a charge jump happened once, it could have happened again in between other successive datasets.

Assuming that G_N is constant upon applying a magnetic field is not valid, especially in a devices where there is evidence for localization (many subgap states are present).

These manipulations were not disclosed in drafts and final versions of the paper.

Conclusions

1. The article claims the presence of QPC's in all devices – but no comprehensive dataset showing unambiguous evidence is present for any device. This is despite a contemporary work involving all three corresponding authors comprehensively demonstrating QPCs.
2. Device selected for inclusion in the paper cannot be distinguished from many other devices from the same fabrication run, other than through the presence of favourable features. These other devices show unambiguous evidence of random QD's being present. However, for the few selected devices, no data is presented that rule out the possibility of favourable features being caused by localized states rather than a QPC.
3. As a result of data selection and processing, only features favourable to a superconducting QPC interpretation are shown. However, all devices show clear evidence for contradicting features through the crossing of faint resonances and discrete subgap resonances. This contradicting evidence was suppressed through data selection and processing and ignored in the discussion of the data in text and figure captions.
4. Several instances of data manipulation have been identified, resulting in e.g. the fabricating of a plateau and 'perfect' quantization.

We believe that the data underpinning this article do not allow for the strong and generic claims made throughout. The article is a result of biased device and data selection, and data manipulation. The claims are not supported. The article should be retracted.